

Reactive Power Limits of Cascaded H-Bridge STATCOMs in Star and Delta Configuration under Negative-Sequence Current Withstanding

Iosu Marzo^{a,*}, Jon Andoni Barrena^a, Alain Sanchez-Ruiz^b, Gonzalo Abad^a, Hector Fernandez-Rebolleda^c, Ignacio Muguruza^a

^aElectronics and Computer Science Department, Mondragon Unibertsitatea, Loramendi 4, Arrasate - Mondragon, 20500, Spain

^bIngeteam R&D Europe, Bizkaia Technology Park 106, Zamudio, 48170, Spain

^cIngeteam Power Technology, Bizkaia Technology Park 110, Zamudio, 48170, Spain

Abstract

Flexible AC Transmission System devices (FATCS) and in particular Static Synchronous Compensators (STATCOM) play a key role in the evolution of the modern power grids to the future smart grids. The STATCOM is used in an increasingly wider variety of scenarios in which the operation under unbalanced conditions stands out. This paper analyzes and compares the reactive power limits of Cascaded H-Bridge (CHB) STATCOMs in star (YCHB) and delta (DCHB) configuration to withstand negative-sequence current. Zero-sequence voltage for the YCHB and zero-sequence current for the DCHB are injected in order to correct the intercluster uneven active power distribution and thus to preserve the dc-link voltage balancing. Both solutions will have an impact on the power rating of the converter. This work clearly quantifies the reactive power limits of each CHB STATCOM configuration depending on the current unbalance at converter terminals, by means of a systematic procedure. Improved explicit expressions of the zero-sequence current in the DCHB are also provided. Experimental results validate the theoretical analysis.

Keywords: Cascaded H-Bridge (CHB), intercluster power balancing, negative-sequence current, Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM), Voltage Source Converter (VSC).

1. Introduction

The Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) using multilevel Voltage Source Converters (VSC) is envisioned as an essential device in both industry and power grid applications. It is used to facilitate the integration of large power consuming loads [1] or renewable energy-sources (RES) [2], by fulfilling the requirements imposed by power system operators. The typical applications of the STATCOM are the improvement of the power system stability, power factor correction, regulation of line voltages, active power filtering, mitigation of voltage flicker, unbalanced load compensation, and low-voltage ride-through (LVRT) [3–5].

Besides common advantages of multilevel VSCs [6], those based on modular structures are today the industrial standard for High Power – Medium Voltage applications. As the ac voltage is proportional to the number of power cells, these structures are scalable, allowing even the transformerless grid-connection [7–9]. Due to the multilevel waveform, the switching frequency can be greatly reduced compared to non-modular VSC topologies, while the converter still achieves excellent harmonic performance [10]. Foremost among these is the Cascaded H-Bridge (CHB) [11], which employment in STATCOM applications has been receiving growing attention.

The CHB structure is composed of multiple units of H-bridge power cells, connected in cascade on their ac side

[6, 7]. The three phase clusters can be connected either in star (YCHB) or in delta (DCHB). The circuit diagrams of both configurations are depicted in Fig. 1. When employing the YCHB, the phase cluster is rated at the line-to-neutral voltage. Thus, when compared with the DCHB, either the number of cascaded power cells can be reduced, or the switching devices can be sized at lower blocking voltage rating to obtain the same ac voltage level. Equivalent behavior can be found in terms of current for the delta case. Another feature to consider is that the DCHB requires a solution (i.e., control loops and/or magnetic elements) to minimize the circulating current inside the delta.

Nowadays, the STATCOM is used for reactive power support in different grid applications. In most cases, the aim of the STATCOM is to provide positive-sequence reactive power (Q^+), by means of generating positive-sequence voltage (v^+) and current (i^+). However, a negative-sequence voltage (v^-) will appear in the point of common coupling (PCC) under unbalanced conditions; for instance, the grid codes permit a small amount of v^- even in steady-state [12, 13]. But in many cases, the STATCOM must operate connected to loads with much severe unbalanced conditions such as metal processing (e.g., arc-furnace loads), mining, or railway traction applications. One alternative to cope with this unbalance could be to generate v^- at the VSC output so the negative-sequence current (i^-) is zero in steady-state, but this increases the digital control burden. Thus, a common choice is to use a classical controller and withstand the generated i^- . That is, if the VSC only provides v^+ and the grid gets unbal-

*Corresponding author

Email address: imarzo@mondragon.edu (Iosu Marzo)

Figure 1: CHB circuit diagrams. (a) YCHB, and (b) DCHB.

anced, i^- will circulate through the device, which should be capable of coping with it in order to remain connected [14]. The amplitude of i^- could be large, it depends on the connection filter impedance and v^- in the PCC, and it might be dominant in those situations where the STATCOM is on standby condition ($i^+ = 0$).

In this scenario, although there is not net energy exchange between the STATCOM and the application, an active power different from zero might appear in each phase of the converter. The CHB presents a major drawback under unbalanced current conditions: the incapacity to exchange active power among phase clusters due to the lack of a common three-phase dc-link. Consequently, dc-link voltages may drift away from their reference values. The unbalance of dc-link capacitor voltages causes higher semiconductor stress or even can provoke isolation failures. This might result in the STATCOM malfunctioning, leading to inject distorted currents into the grid, and even to exceed the operating limits.

The adopted power balancing strategy needs to guarantee constant dc-link capacitor voltages. First of all, an equal active power distribution among phase clusters needs to be ensured (*intercluster balancing*) [15]. Secondly, dc

voltages of the power cells forming each phase cluster need to be balanced (*intracluster balancing*) [16–18]. This paper deals with the first one, since the intracluster balancing in CHB structures needs to be addressed regardless of whether it is i^- or not.

The intercluster active power balancing in the YCHB can be addressed by adding a fundamental-frequency zero-sequence voltage (v_0^Y) [19–21]. That is why the operating range of the star during unbalanced conditions is limited by the available dc-side voltage. Regarding the DCHB, a fundamental-frequency zero-sequence current (i_0) can be injected inside the delta to correct the uneven active power distribution among phase clusters [22–25].

Several references have compared the power balancing capabilities of both CHB STATCOM configurations by means of quantifying the required v_0^Y in the YCHB and i_0 in the DCHB [26–30]. Both the presence of i^- , and the injection of v_0^Y or i_0 will limit the maximum power that the STATCOM could deliver to the grid. From the STATCOM manufacturer point of view, the reactive power limit is the indicative parameter to compare and select the most appropriate CHB configuration. To the best knowledge of the authors, the quantification of this limit cannot be found in the specialized literature. So, the main contribution of this paper is to quantify the Q^+ limits of the YCHB and DCHB STATCOMs as a function of the current unbalance.

Also, some of these references compare the YCHB and the DCHB in an analogous but different scenario; e.g., YCHB under unbalanced current and DCHB under unbalanced voltage. In this paper both YCHB and DCHB configurations are fairly compared in the same operating scenario. Moreover, most of these references validate their comparisons in a reduced power rating experimental set-up. In this paper the results are validated in a real-scale prototype in a Medium Voltage Laboratory. Additionally, the explicit expressions of i_0 in the DCHB have been derived considering also the filters inside the delta (L_f).

Summarizing, this paper aims to analyze and compare the reactive power limits of CHB-based STATCOMs in star and delta configuration for i^- withstanding, by means of the following contributions:

1. The Q^+ limits of the YCHB and DCHB STATCOMs for i^- withstanding are generically quantified. To do so, a systematic procedure is proposed. These limits allow comparing both configurations and concluding which one is more suitable for a certain scenario.
2. Both YCHB and DCHB configurations are fairly compared in the same operating scenario. Besides, this paper extends the analysis to operating points where i^- exceeds i^+ , which is not found in the literature.
3. Derivation of the explicit expressions of the required i_0 in the DCHB considering the zero-sequence voltage drop across the filters inside the delta (L_f). This assumption is crucial in order to be precise in the calculation of i_0 .
4. Experimental validation in a 100 kVA prototype.

The rest of the paper is outlined as follows. Section 2 presents the i^- withstanding scenario and its impact on

CHB-based STATCOMs. The intercluster active power balancing solution and the overall control design are described in Section 3. Section 4 proposes a procedure to quantify and compares the reactive power limits of both configurations. Detailed experimental results under various i^- withstanding scenarios are presented in Section 5 to verify the theoretical limits of YCHB and DCHB STATCOMs. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Impact of Negative-Sequence Current on Cascaded H-Bridge Structures

Generally speaking, the per-phase instantaneous active power of the converter can be calculated by the inner product of the phase voltage and current:

$$p_{ph}(t) = \tilde{p}_{ph}(t) + \bar{P}_{ph} \quad \text{where } ph = a, b, c. \quad (1)$$

The resulting active power contains both an oscillating (\tilde{p}_{ph}) and an average term (\bar{P}_{ph}). The first oscillates at twice the grid frequency (2ω) with a zero average value. In turn, considering the negative-sequence current component, the average term can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P}_{ph} = & \underbrace{\frac{V^+ I^+}{2} \cos(\delta_v^+ - \theta_i^+)}_{\bar{P}_{ph}^{++}} \\ & + \underbrace{\frac{V^+ I^-}{2} \cos\left(\delta_v^+ - \theta_i^- + k \frac{4\pi}{3}\right)}_{\bar{P}_{ph}^{+-}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $k = 0, -1, 1$ for $ph = a, b, c$, respectively. V^+ and δ_v^+ denote the converter phase cluster positive-sequence voltage phasor amplitude and angle. Likewise, I^+ , I^- , θ_i^+ and θ_i^- are the converter phase cluster positive- and negative-sequence current phasor amplitudes and angles, respectively.

The main characteristic of the STATCOM application is that there is no need of any energy-source, since, neglecting losses, the net active power transfer between the converter and the power grid is zero; i.e., $\bar{P}_a + \bar{P}_b + \bar{P}_c = 0$. Furthermore, as long as there is no cross-interaction between positive- and negative-sequence components, the average active power which flows into each phase cluster is also zero ($\bar{P}_{ph} = 0$).

As Fig. 2 shows, if the VSC-based STATCOM is not designed to control v^- (since it is required to provide Q^+) and the PCC gets unbalanced, a negative-sequence current is generated and circulates through the power converter, which should be capable of withstanding in order to remain connected [14]. Even if the amount of v^- in the PCC is not large (0.02 – 0.03 p.u. [12, 13]), it can induce a significant i^- (0.2 – 0.3 p.u.), considering typical MV connection filter ($L_{f,g}$) impedance values (0.1 – 0.2 p.u.).

In this scenario, term \bar{P}_{ph}^{+-} arises in (2), which is also different in each phase. This means that phase clusters may deliver or absorb an active power different from zero ($\bar{P}_a \neq \bar{P}_b \neq \bar{P}_c \neq 0$). Due to the fact that under unbalanced current conditions the sum of term \bar{P}_{ph}^{+-} in the three

Figure 2: Negative-sequence current (i^-) withstanding scenario.

Figure 3: Effect of i^- on the DCHB STATCOM. At $t = 60$ ms the current becomes unbalanced. (a) Phase cluster instantaneous active power, and (b) phase cluster instantaneous dc-link capacitor voltages.

phase clusters is still zero ($\bar{P}_a + \bar{P}_b + \bar{P}_c = 0$), converter structures with a common three-phase dc-link (e.g., the 3L NPC [31]) do not need any energy-source for STATCOM application, whatever the negative-sequence current is. In contrast, the main disadvantage of CHB structures is the lack of a common three-phase dc-link, and thereby the difficulty in exchanging active power among phase clusters. Consequently, countermeasures must be taken in order to correct this uneven active power distribution. Otherwise, dc-link voltage balancing in each phase cluster cannot be guaranteed under unbalanced current conditions.

With the aim of showing the effect of this operating scenario, the DCHB STATCOM is simulated withstanding a negative-sequence current. Fig. 3 shows the instantaneous active power flowing into each phase cluster of the converter (p_{ab} , p_{bc} , p_{ca}), as well as the dc-link capacitor voltages of each power cell (v_{dc-ab} , v_{dc-bc} , v_{dc-ca}). For the sake of simplicity, each phase cluster is composed of a single power cell. The plotted capacitor voltages are low-pass filtered as well, in order to remove the double-frequency component (2ω) for clarity of the illustration. It can be appreciated that when the current becomes unbalanced, non-zero average active powers appear in each phase cluster, which lead to the drifting of dc-side voltages. The effect in the YCHB is almost identical.

In order to quantify the weight of i^- , the ratio of current unbalance (k_{ipn}) is defined [31]. Equation (3) is applied when the positive-sequence current component predominates, and (4) when the negative-sequence does. $k_{ipn} = 0$ states that the current sequence is only positive; $k_{ipn} = 1$ that both components exist and are of equal magnitude ($I^+ = I^-$); and $k_{ipn} = 2$ expresses that all current is negative-sequence.

$$\text{for } I^+ \geq I^- \rightarrow k_{ipn} = \frac{I^-}{I^+} \rightarrow 0 \leq k_{ipn} \leq 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{for } I^+ \leq I^- \rightarrow k_{ipn} = 2 - \frac{I^+}{I^-} \rightarrow 1 \leq k_{ipn} \leq 2 \quad (4)$$

In the applications in which it is required to provide reactive power, the STATCOM is normally on standby situation and no providing any Q^+ ($i^+ = 0$). In this scenario, the appearance of any minimum v^- in the PCC will induce a i^- and the converter will start its operation with $k_{ipn} = 2$. That is why it is important to extend the analysis to operating points where i^- exceeds i^+ ($k_{ipn} > 1$).

3. Intercluster Active Power Balancing

The intercluster active power balancing control must guarantee that the active power is equally distributed among phase clusters, compensating for the system losses as well as maintaining the charge of the dc-link capacitors. The adopted intercluster active power balancing strategy depends on the CHB circuit configuration.

3.1. Solution for the Star-Connected Cascaded H-Bridge

To overcome the issue of withstanding i^- in the YCHB STATCOM, a fundamental-frequency common zero-sequence voltage (v_0^Y) can be injected into the converter star point N. The addition of this component does not affect the three-phase voltages and currents at grid side, and allows two degrees of freedom; its amplitude (V_0^Y), and angle ($\delta_{v_0^Y}$):

$$v_0^Y(t) = V_0^Y \sin(\omega t + \delta_{v_0^Y}) \quad (5)$$

Considering v_0^Y , and assuming that the VSC is not able to synthesize v^- , the phasors of the converter phase cluster voltage and current are defined as

$$\bar{V}_{ph} = V^+ e^{j(\delta_v^+ + 2\pi k/3)} + V_0^Y e^{j\delta_{v_0^Y}} \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{I}_{ph} = I^+ e^{j(\theta_i^+ + 2\pi k/3)} + I^- e^{j(\theta_i^- - 2\pi k/3)} \quad (7)$$

being $k = 0, -1, 1$ for $ph = a, b, c$ (star case), respectively. The aim is to find an appropriate V_0^Y and $\delta_{v_0^Y}$ so as to generate an average active power term (\bar{P}_{0-ph}^{YCHB}). This term will cancel out the effect of the non-zero average active power at each phase cluster due to the interaction between negative- and positive-sequence components (term \bar{P}_{ph}^{+-}), as well as it will compensate for any type of power disturbance caused by non-idealities (\bar{P}_{dis}):

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P}_{0-ph}^{YCHB} &= \frac{V_0^Y I^+}{2} \cos\left(\delta_{v_0^Y} - \theta_i^+ - k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ &+ \frac{V_0^Y I^-}{2} \cos\left(\delta_{v_0^Y} - \theta_i^- + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ &= - \underbrace{\frac{V^+ I^-}{2} \cos\left(\delta_v^+ - \theta_i^- + k \frac{4\pi}{3}\right)}_{\bar{P}_{ph}^{+-}} + \bar{P}_{dis-ph} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

It is worth noting that term \bar{P}_{ph}^{+-} in (2) is common in the three phase clusters, so it is controlled through the overall dc-link voltage control (see Subsection 3.3). In order to isolate the terms derived by the injection of v_0^Y , (8) can be developed as

$$V_0^Y (K_2^{ph} \cos \delta_{v_0^Y} + K_3^{ph} \sin \delta_{v_0^Y}) = -K_1^{ph} + \bar{P}_{dis-ph} \quad (9)$$

where the following constant terms are defined:

$$\begin{aligned} K_1^{ph} &= \underbrace{V^+ I^- \cos\left(\delta_v^+ - \theta_i^- + k \frac{4\pi}{3}\right)}_{\bar{P}_{ph}^{+-}} \\ K_2^{ph} &= I^+ \cos\left(\theta_i^+ + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + I^- \cos\left(\theta_i^- - k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ K_3^{ph} &= I^+ \sin\left(\theta_i^+ + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + I^- \sin\left(\theta_i^- - k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Any two of the three active power equations in (8) can be used to determine the explicit expression of the angle $\delta_{v_0^Y}$ [28]. Considering phase clusters a and b:

$$\tan \delta_{v_0^Y} = \frac{(\bar{P}_{dis-b} - K_1^b)K_2^a - (\bar{P}_{dis-a} - K_1^a)K_2^b}{(\bar{P}_{dis-a} - K_1^a)K_3^b - (\bar{P}_{dis-b} - K_1^b)K_3^a} \quad (11)$$

Simplifying (9), and substituting the calculated $\delta_{v_0^Y}$, the amplitude V_0^Y can be derived as [28]

$$V_0^Y = \frac{\bar{P}_{dis-ph} - K_1^{ph}}{K_2^{ph} \cos \delta_{v_0^Y} + K_3^{ph} \sin \delta_{v_0^Y}} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 4 (a) shows the evolution of the required zero-sequence voltage amplitude (V_0^Y) as a function of k_{ipn} and the angle between the current sequences ($\theta_{ipn} = \theta_i^- - \theta_i^+$) in a YCHB STATCOM, regardless of whether it is operating as capacitive or inductive power factor. For the simulated ideal case, \bar{P}_{dis} has been neglected, and the most restrictive phase cluster current is set to the rated one. It can be observed that V_0^Y tends to infinity when $I^+ = I^-$ [28]. That is, if $k_{ipn} = 1$, theoretically infinity voltage is required to keep dc-link voltages balanced. Normally, the ratio of current unbalance is the operating requirement for which the converter is dimensioned, regardless of the angle θ_{ipn} . Fig. 4 (b) illustrates the maximum and minimum V_0^Y for each k_{ipn} .

In a real application, the injection of v_0^Y could lead the converter voltage exceeding its rated level, and thus resulting in the YCHB operating in over-modulation or even becoming uncontrollable. That is, the zero-sequence voltage can be injected until the maximum attainable output voltage is reached. The amplitude modulation index (m_a) will

Figure 4: Required zero-sequence voltage amplitude in the YCHB STATCOM ($V^+ = 1$ p.u., and $\max(|\bar{I}_{ph}|) = 1$ p.u.). (a) As a function of k_{ipn} and θ_{ipn} , and (b) max. and min. V_0^Y for each k_{ipn} .

Figure 5: k_{ipn} operation area of the YCHB STATCOM as function of m_a . Points which the converter can operate are illustrated in green, while the voltage limit is reached in those drawn in red.

determine the maximum i^- (and thus k_{ipn}) that the converter could withstand without losing the controllability of dc-link capacitor voltages. Fig. 5 depicts the theoretical operation area of the YCHB STATCOM. If the voltage limit is reached, the converter can be over-rated either serializing more power cells or increasing the dc-link voltage.

3.2. Solution for the Delta-Connected Cascaded H-Bridge

For the DCHB STATCOM a fundamental-frequency zero-sequence current (i_0) can be injected to guarantee an uniform active power distribution among phase clusters. Analogous to the aforementioned v_0^Y injection in the star, the injected i_0 circulates only inside the delta, without affecting the grid side. It also allows two degrees of freedom in terms of its amplitude (I_0), and angle (θ_{i_0}):

$$i_0(t) = I_0 \sin(\omega t + \theta_{i_0}) \quad (13)$$

Assuming that the VSC does not include v^- control loops as in the YCHB, the phasors of the converter phase cluster voltage and current are expressed in (14) and (15); being $k = 0, -1, 1$ for $ph = ab, bc, ca$ (delta case), respectively.

$$\bar{V}_{ph} = V^+ e^{j(\delta_v^+ + 2\pi k/3)} + V_0^\Delta e^{j\delta_{v_0^\Delta}} \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{I}_{ph} = I^+ e^{j(\theta_i^+ + 2\pi k/3)} + I^- e^{j(\theta_i^- - 2\pi k/3)} + I_0 e^{j\theta_{i_0}} \quad (15)$$

The injected i_0 will generate a zero-sequence voltage drop across the filters inside the delta (L_f). Thus, the converter must generate also a zero-sequence voltage (v_0^Δ) to compensate for this term so that it does not affect the grid-side ac voltage, as seen in (14). In this sense, the intercluster active power balancing control needs to generate this zero-sequence voltage, which will lead to the calculated i_0 , (see Subsection 3.3). Notice that v_0^Δ is much smaller than v_0^Y since in the DCHB the zero-sequence voltage is only responsible for creating the zero-sequence current rather than distributing the active power among phase clusters. As Fig. 7 shows, it is essential to consider v_0^Δ and the value of L_f in the expressions of i_0 in order to be accurate in the calculation; a fact that has not been contemplated in previous investigations.

Analogously to the star, the required i_0 will generate an average active power term (\bar{P}_{0-ph}^{DCHB}) which will guarantee that the active power is equally distributed among delta-connected clusters, while it preserves the dc-link voltages in each phase cluster adjusted to the reference value:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P}_{0-ph}^{DCHB} &= \frac{V^+ I_0}{2} \cos\left(\delta_v^+ - \theta_{i_0} + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ &+ \frac{V_0^\Delta I^+}{2} \cos\left(\delta_{v_0^\Delta} - \theta_i^+ - k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ &+ \frac{V_0^\Delta I^-}{2} \cos\left(\delta_{v_0^\Delta} - \theta_i^- + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ &+ \frac{V_0^\Delta I_0}{2} \cos\left(\delta_{v_0^\Delta} - \theta_{i_0}\right) \\ &= - \underbrace{\frac{V^+ I^-}{2} \cos\left(\delta_v^+ - \theta_i^- + k \frac{4\pi}{3}\right)}_{\bar{P}_{ph}^{+-}} + \bar{P}_{dis-ph} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Following the same procedure adopted for the YCHB, and considering the filters inside the delta purely inductive (L_f) to facilitate the calculation, the explicit expressions of I_0 and θ_{i_0} can be given by

$$\tan \theta_{i_0} = \frac{(\bar{P}_{dis-bc} - K_1^{bc})K_2^{ab} - (\bar{P}_{dis-ab} - K_1^{ab})K_2^{bc}}{(\bar{P}_{dis-ab} - K_1^{ab})K_3^{bc} - (\bar{P}_{dis-bc} - K_1^{bc})K_3^{ab}} \quad (17)$$

$$I_0 = \frac{\bar{P}_{dis-ph} - K_1^{ph}}{K_2^{ph} \cos \theta_{i_0} + K_3^{ph} \sin \theta_{i_0}} \quad (18)$$

being $X_f = \omega L_f$, and the constant terms the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
K_1^{ph} &= \underbrace{V^+ I^- \cos\left(\delta_v^+ - \theta_i^- + k \frac{4\pi}{3}\right)}_{\bar{P}_{ph}^{+-}} \\
K_2^{ph} &= K_4^{ph} + X_f K_7^{ph} & K_3^{ph} &= K_5^{ph} + X_f K_6^{ph} \\
K_4^{ph} &= V^+ \cos\left(\delta_v^+ + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\
K_5^{ph} &= V^+ \sin\left(\delta_v^+ + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\
K_6^{ph} &= I^+ \cos\left(\theta_i^+ + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + I^- \cos\left(\theta_i^- - k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\
K_7^{ph} &= I^+ \sin\left(\theta_i^+ + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + I^- \sin\left(\theta_i^- - k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

It should be noted that by this resolution method, considering the zero-sequence voltage drop inside the delta (v_0^Δ) and modifying the values of the constants, the same equations are obtained for v_0^Y in the YCHB and i_0 in the DCHB.

The evolution of the required zero-sequence current amplitude (I_0) in the DCHB STATCOM is shown in Fig. 6. Note that the maximum I_0 is demanded when $k_{ipn} = 1.5$; i.e., when $I^- = 2I^+$. The injected i_0 involves a current de-rating so as not to exceed the rated value of switching devices, which forces to reduce the converter i^+ (and thus the available positive-sequence reactive power). However, in contrast to the YCHB, the DCHB converter can stay connected to that PCC maintaining its nominal ac voltage up to 100% current de-rating, without the necessity of changing m_a . Besides, although the calculation of the required i_0 in the DCHB presents a singular point where

Figure 6: Required zero-sequence current amplitude in the DCHB STATCOM ($V^+ = 1$ p.u., and $\max(|\bar{I}_{ph}|) = 1$ p.u.). (a) As a function of k_{ipn} and θ_{ipn} , and (b) max. and min. I_0 for each k_{ipn} .

Figure 7: Required zero-sequence current max. and min. amplitude in the DCHB STATCOM for each k_{ipn} and for different inductive filter values inside the delta ($V^+ = 1$ p.u., and $\max(|\bar{I}_{ph}|) = 1$ p.u.).

the converter cannot operate in other scenarios (e.g., when $V^+ = V^-$ [28]), it does not present any in this i^- withstanding scenario.

3.3. Overall Control Design

The operation of CHB converters for STATCOM application and i^- withstanding requires controllers in order to address both the overall dc-link voltage unbalance and the intercluster active power unbalance. Fig. 8 shows the overall control structure of the STATCOM, which can be applied either to the YCHB or the DCHB configurations. This is composed of three main parts: the dual vector control, the overall dc-link voltage control, and the intercluster active power balancing control. However, dual vector control is sometimes simplified to the positive control loop.

Three-phase grid currents ($i_{g,abc}$) are decomposed into positive- and negative-sequences, and are transformed to the dq -reference frame using the transformation angle ($\theta = \omega t$) provided by the phase-locked loop (PLL), which synchronizes the STATCOM with the positive-sequence grid voltage (v_g^+). The positive- and negative-sequence dq components of the measured current are estimated using the delayed signal cancellation (DSC) technique, and the dual vector control allows to control both sequences independently (tuned as [32]). The obtained converter reference voltages are then transformed to three-phase quantities (v_{ph}^{+*}), and the converter switching pattern is obtained; in this case, through a pulse-width modulation (PWM).

The overall dc-link voltage controller is required to absorb the sufficient three-phase active power from the power grid (\bar{P}_g^*) to compensate for power losses and non-idealities across the converter. It generates the necessary d -component positive-sequence current (i_d^{+*}) for maintaining the average dc-link voltage adjusted at the reference value (v_{dc-ph}^*).

The equality of the three-phase dc-link voltages is guaranteed by the intercluster active power balancing control [28]. When using the YCHB, the required v_0^{Y*} is calculated according the i^- to withstand, and the power disturbances in each phase cluster (\bar{P}_{dis-ph}^*) generated by the intercluster dc voltage control, from (11) and (12). Analogously, the required i_0^* in the DCHB is calculated from (17) and (18). As mentioned, power disturbance references of two phase clusters are enough for calculating the phase angles $\delta_{v_0^Y}$ in (11) and θ_{i_0} in (17). Note that while the

Figure 8: Simplified block diagram of the overall control design for both YCHB and DCHB STATCOMs.

calculated v_0^{Y*} in the YCHB can be directly added to the output reference voltages of the dual vector control (v_{ph}^{+*}), when using the DCHB, a proportional resonant controller (PR) tuned at ω is necessary to generate the $v_0^{\Delta*}$ that leads to the calculated i_0^* [33, 34]. PR controllers allow to track sinusoidal references of certain frequencies with zero steady-state error [35].

4. Reactive Power Limits

As mathematically demonstrated, additional fundamental-frequency zero-sequence voltage (YCHB) or current (DCHB) can be injected to deal with i^- , both of which vary depending on k_{ipn} and θ_{ipn} . In this context, the VSC will be limited in terms of voltage and/or current for STATCOM application. However, the values of v_0^Y and i_0 are not significant to quantify and compare which CHB configuration is the most appropriate for this scenario. As the aim of the STATCOM is to provide positive-sequence reactive power (Q^+), this is, from a dimensioning point of view, the indicative parameter to select the most suitable configuration. Note that the effect of the 2ω dc-link capacitor voltage fluctuation in the Q^+ limits is negligible in single-phase dc-link VSC topologies such as CHBs [36].

Fig. 9 shows the systematic procedure to quantify Q^+ in each CHB STATCOM configuration, and Fig. 10 shows the Q^+ limits of each configuration for i^- withstanding; i.e., the limit for each k_{ipn} , for the most restrictive θ_{ipn} angle. This is the main contribution of the paper. The theoretical maximum attainable Q^+ is also provided.

On the one hand, the Q^+ limits of the YCHB STATCOM are calculated as follows (see Fig. 9):

Figure 9: Flow chart of the procedure to quantify Q^+ in each CHB STATCOM configuration.

- Step 1. The positive-sequence voltage amplitude (V^+) generated in the YCHB depends on the amplitude modulation index (m_a) using.
- Step 2. Then, for each k_{ipn} and θ_{ipn} , the required \bar{V}_0 is calculated from (11) and (12).
- Step 3. As mentioned, the YCHB cannot operate

Figure 10: Positive-sequence reactive power (Q^+) limits of YCHB and DCHB configurations for STATCOM application with i^- withstanding.

when the converter phase cluster voltage exceeds its rated level ($\max |\bar{V}_{ph}| \leq V_{ph-nom}$). That is why voltage over-rating is sometimes required so as to increase the available dc-side voltage.

The plotted line in Fig. 10 illustrates the theoretical Q^+ limit of the correctly voltage over-rated YCHB for each k_{ipn} . As this voltage over-rating is not feasible in practice, limits for the YCHB configuration with practical voltage ratings are also served (different m_a values); dashed lines represent k_{ipn} operating points where the voltage limit is reached and the converter is not able to work. For instance, it can be seen that with $m_a = 0.9$ (which can be case of a grid-connected STATCOM), the YCHB cannot withstand a negative-sequence current up to $k_{ipn} = 0.1$. In this configuration, the power de-rating is due to the i^+ decreasing as k_{ipn} increases. An important drawback is that as infinity V_0^Y is required in the operating point $k_{ipn} = 1$ [28], beyond this singular point, the YCHB becomes uncontrollable in practical applications. Thus, it can be concluded that the capability of the YCHB STATCOM to withstand i^- is strongly limited by the voltage rating of its phase clusters.

On the other hand, Fig. 9 also summarizes the procedure to obtain the Q^+ limits of the DCHB STATCOM:

- Step 1. In contrast with the YCHB, the delta configuration does not present any limitation in terms of exceeding the rated voltage; as long as it has a few margin to compensate for the zero-sequence voltage drop across the filters inside the delta (v_0^Δ). In other words, the (m_a) used does not imply any limitation for the DCHB. That is why, in this scenario, it can remain connected to the PCC guaranteeing the nominal ac voltage up to 100% de-rating of i^+ ($Q^+ = 0$), as the grid code might demand.
- Step 2. The required \bar{I}_0 is calculated from (17) and (18), depending on k_{ipn} and θ_{ipn} .
- Step 3. The i^+ limit (I_{der}^+) is calculated by making the most charged phase cluster have the rated value

$$(I_{ph-nom}).$$

Therefore, the line plotted in Fig. 10 decreases when k_{ipn} increases either as a result of the phase cluster i^+ de-rating due to the increasing of i_0 , and/or the decreasing of i^+ as i^- increases. In this scenario the Q^+ p.u. limit is equal to the I^+ p.u. limit. The major advantage over the star is that the DCHB can deal with severe inter-cluster active power unbalances guaranteeing the controllability of dc-link capacitor voltages; even at $k_{ipn} \gg 1$. Besides, note that the delta configuration does not present any singular point which might cause the STATCOM to lose controllability, as long as there is no v^- at the converter terminals.

5. Experimental Results

Experimental results obtained from a 500 V – 100 kVA three-phase 5-level Neutral Point Clamped H-bridge (5L NPC/HB) [37] converter prototype are provided to demonstrate the intercluster active power balancing capabilities and Q^+ limits of both YCHB and DCHB STATCOMs when withstanding i^- . The 5L NPC/HB power cell is commonly employed in the CHB topology in order to increase the power rating [31]. Note that the conclusions drawn are valid regardless of the topology used in the power cell.

The simplified circuit diagrams of the YCHB and the DCHB, as well as the layout of the downscaled experimental set-up built in the Medium Voltage Laboratory of Ingeteam Power Technology S.A. (Zamudio, Spain) are shown in Figs. 11 (a), (b), and (c), respectively. The parameters of the prototype and the experiments are also given in Table I.

Each phase cluster is composed of a single 5L NPC/HB power cell ($n = 1$), with the aim of isolating the analyzed intercluster balancing control. The switching scheme used is the multilevel SPWM with a switching frequency of 1 kHz. In order to reach the voltage limit and demonstrate the power limits, the converter nominal voltage of

the YCHB has been limited to its half; hence, $Q^+ = 1$ p.u. and $m_a = 1$ correspond to the Q^+ and m_a achieved with this voltage. Similarly, the nominal current in the DCHB has also been limited to its half.

By a common scalar voltage/frequency regulation (thus, the dual vector control of Fig. 8 is not used), the 5L NPC/HB converter synthesizes positive-sequence voltage (v^+), and connected to unbalanced inductive loads ($L_{load-ph}$), i^- circulation is generated through the converter phase clusters. For these tests, 3.2 mH and 7.5 mH single-phase loads are combined so as to generate different k_{ipn} and θ_{ipn} operating points. It should be remarked that using different combinations of passive single-phase inductive loads, it is not possible to generate operating points where I^- exceeds I^+ ; that is why the ratio k_{ipn} is less than the unity in the carried out experiments.

In the carried out experiments, since the VSC is not connected to the grid, and is feeding passive inductive loads, it is necessary to have an energy-source connected to the dc-links. That is why these experiments are performed using a 12-pulse Diode Front End (DFE) rectifier connected to each power cell. For the results that this paper aims to validate these experiments are valid. If the

intercluster active power balancing strategy does not regulate properly, the dc-link capacitor voltages will remain unbalanced, and even some of the dc-link voltages could continuously increase above the dc voltage set by the DFE rectifier. Therefore, the overall dc-link control of Fig. 8 is not needed for these experiments.

Table 1: Experimental Prototype Parameters

Parameter	Value
Rated power (S_n)	100 kVA
Rated voltage (V_{ll-rms})	500 V
Power cell dc-link voltage (V_{dc})	430 V
Power cell dc-link capacitor ($C_{d1} = C_{d2}$)	1.65 mF
Num. of power cells per phase cluster (n)	1
Power cell topology	5L NPC/HB
Filter inductor in the DCHB (L_f)	2.5 mH
Output fundamental-frequency (f)	50 Hz
Switching frequency (f_{sw})	1 kHz

Figure 11: Experimental prototype layout. (a) Simplified circuit diagram of the YCHB, (b) simplified circuit diagram of the DCHB, and (c) prototype scheme.

Figure 12: Experimental results of the YCHB with $L_{load-a} = L_{load-b} = 7.5$ mH and $L_{load-c} = 10.7$ mH ($k_{ipn} = 0.12$, $\theta_{ipn} = 60^\circ$).

Figure 13: Experimental results of the YCHB with $L_{load-a} = L_{load-b} = 3.2$ mH and $L_{load-c} = 7.5$ mH ($k_{ipn} = 0.31$, $\theta_{ipn} = 60^\circ$).

Assuming that the DFE rectifier will provide the active power consumed by all the resistive components of the prototype, this experimental set-up emulates the i^- withstanding scenario of a STATCOM application. Note that although in the following experiments the STATCOM is operating with capacitive power factor (connected to inductive loads), the results with inductive power factor are the same. For the DCHB, 2.5 mH single-phase inductive filters (L_f) are used inside the delta.

All the tests performed are constituted of three stages:

1. Firstly, the converter withstands i^- without activating the intercluster active power balancing control. During this interval, dc-link voltages (v_{dc-ph}) drift from their reference values. Without the DFE rectifier, at least one of the dc capacitors would discharge.
2. When the intercluster active power balancing control is activated, dc-link voltages in each phase cluster are equalized. At this point, the converter operates within its limits. Note that dc-link voltages vary from one experiment to another, because they depend on the loads connected to the laboratory ac grid.
3. Finally, the voltage reference is increased and the converter limits are reached. As a consequence, dc-link capacitor voltages begin to drift away.

Figs. 12 and 13 show the experimental results of the YCHB under two i^- withstanding scenarios. In Figs. 12

Figure 14: Q^+ operating transitions of Figs. 12 and 13 ($\theta_{ipn} = 60^\circ$).

(a) and 13 (a) the injected zero-sequence voltage (v_0^Y) and the amplitude modulation index (m_a) are plotted. It can be seen that in Fig. 12 (a) m_a goes from 0.85 to 0.95; likewise, in Fig. 13 (a) m_a goes from 0.75 to 0.85. Figs. 12 (b) and 13 (b) depict the dc-link voltages of each phase cluster. As expected, these dc voltages contain both an average and a double-frequency component (2ω) value. The injected v_0^Y acts over the average one, which is generated by the average active power component. Figs. 12 (c) and 13 (c) show the line-to-line voltages of each experiment,

Figure 15: Experimental results of the DCHB with $L_{load-a} = L_{load-b} = 3.2$ mH and $L_{load-c} = 10.7$ mH ($k_{ipn} = 0.38$, $\theta_{ipn} = 0^\circ$).

which are not modified when injecting v_0^Y . The load currents are also served in Figs. 12 (d) and 13 (d), which are clearly unbalanced but are not altered by injecting v_0^Y . A transition is made from an operating point where the converter does not exceed its Q^+ limit (green cross), to another point where it does (red cross), as Fig. 14 summarizes, thus validating the analysis in Fig. 10. It can be seen that dc-link voltages begin to drift away when there is no available voltage for the injection of v_0^Y . When the operating limits of the converter are exceeded, the dc-link voltages would increase until the converter would stop due to overvoltage. Thus, for safety reasons, the injected v_0^Y is saturated once the limit is reached and not set to 0.

Regarding the DCHB, the experimental results are illustrated in Figs. 15 and 16. Analogous to the YCHB, the injected zero-sequence current (i_0) and the positive-sequence current phasor amplitude (I^+) are shown. Since the Q^+ de-rating of the delta configuration is only influ-

Figure 16: Experimental results of the DCHB with $L_{load-a} = L_{load-b} = 3.2$ mH and $L_{load-c} = 18.2$ mH ($k_{ipn} = 0.55$, $\theta_{ipn} = 0^\circ$).

Figure 17: I^+ operating transitions of Figs. 15 and 16 ($\theta_{ipn} = 0^\circ$). Solid bars represent the I^+ , I^- and I_0 required in each point.

enced by the de-rating of i^+ (see Fig. 9), the operating transitions are made by increasing the value of I^+ ; in Fig.

15 (a) I^+ goes from 0.5 to 0.7 p.u., while in Fig. 16 (a) is increased from 0.4 to 0.6. The injected zero-sequence voltage amplitude (v_0^Δ) that leads to the reference i_0 is also served in Figs. 15 (b) and 16 (b), which is saturated once the limit is reached as in the star case. Figs. 15 (d) and 16 (d) show the output line-to-line voltages, which are not affected by the injected v_0^Δ . It can be seen in the load currents of Figs. 15 (e) and 16 (e) that the injected i_0 circulates only inside the delta. As Fig. 17 depicts, which its I^+ per unit limit is equal to the Q^+ per unit limit of Fig. 10, the current limit is exceeded due to the required i_0 . As the converter is not able to inject this i_0 , dc-link voltage balancing cannot be guaranteed in each phase cluster, as Figs. 15 (c) and 16 (c) show.

The shown experimental results summarize twelve operating points in Figs. 12, 13, 15 and 16, and the transitions between them. It can be seen how the achieved results of both configurations meet the theoretical approach.

6. Conclusion

Knowing the power limits of the converter is a key issue when selecting the most suitable configuration for a certain application. Some applications which require a CHB STATCOM may demand to withstand i^- . In this framework, the use of the CHB implies the addition of a zero-sequence voltage (YCHB) or current (DCHB) so as to distribute equally the active power among phase clusters. This paper has presented a systematic procedure to theoretically quantify and has compared the reactive power limits of both YCHB and DCHB configurations for STATCOM application with i^- withstanding.

The carried out analysis confirms the DCHB as the preferable option for STATCOM application dealing with severe unbalanced current conditions. While the YCHB is strongly limited by the available dc-side voltage, the DCHB can stay connected to the PCC regardless the i^- to withstand. The comparison presented has been supported by experimental results which validate the theoretical analysis under different k_{ipn} values.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported in part by the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training of Spain under Grant FPU18/04246, and in part by the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Tourism of Spain through the Project "Grid Ancillary Services Autonomous Converter (GASAC)" under Grant RTC-2017-26091-3.

References

- [1] B. K. Bose, "Power electronics and motor drives recent progress and perspective," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 581–588, 2009.
- [2] J. M. Carrasco *et al.*, "Power-electronic systems for the grid integration of renewable energy sources: a survey," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 1002–1016, 2006.
- [3] D. Soto and T. C. Green, "A comparison of high-power converter topologies for the implementation of FACTS controllers," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 1072–1080, 2002.
- [4] A. Balikci and E. Akpınar, "A multilevel converter with reduced number of switches in STATCOM for load balancing," *Electr. Power Syst. Res.*, vol. 123, pp. 164–173, 2015.
- [5] S. N. Duarte, F. T. Ghatti, P. M. de Almeida, and P. G. Barbosa, "Zero-sequence voltage compensation of a distribution network through a four-wire modular multilevel static synchronous compensator," *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 109, pp. 57–72, 2019.
- [6] S. Kouro *et al.*, "Recent advances and industrial applications of multilevel converters," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 57, no. 8, pp. 2553–2580, 2010.
- [7] M. Malinowski, K. Gopakumar, J. Rodriguez, and M. A. Perez, "A survey on cascaded multilevel inverters," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 57, no. 7, pp. 2197–2206, 2010.
- [8] H. Akagi, "Classification, terminology, and application of the modular multilevel cascade converter (MMCC)," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 26, no. 11, pp. 3119–3130, 2011.
- [9] P. Hu, J. M. Guerrero, and Z. He, "Design and analysis of a transformerless STATCOM based on hybrid cascaded multilevel converter," *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 104, pp. 694–704, 2019.
- [10] Y. Cheng, C. Qian, M. L. Crow, S. Pekarek, and S. Atcitty, "A comparison of diode-clamped and cascaded multilevel converters for a STATCOM with energy storage," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 53, no. 5, pp. 1512–1521, 2006.
- [11] F. Z. Peng, J.-S. Lai, J. W. McKeever, and J. VanCoevering, "A multilevel voltage-source inverter with separate DC sources for static VAR generation," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 1130–1138, 1996.
- [12] IEC 61000-2-4, "Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 2-4: Environment - Compatibility levels in industrial plants for low-frequency conducted disturbances," 2004.
- [13] ANSI C84.1, "Electric Power Systems Voltage Ratings (60 Hz)," 2020.
- [14] I. Marzo, A. Sanchez-Ruiz, J. A. Barrena, G. Abad, and I. Muguruza, "Power balancing in cascaded H-bridge and modular multilevel converters under unbalanced operation: A review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 110 525–110 543, 2021.
- [15] R. E. Betz, T. Summers, and T. Furney, "Symmetry compensation using a H-bridge multilevel STATCOM with zero sequence injection," in *41st IAS Annu. Meet. Conf. Rec. 2006 Ind. Appl. Conf.*, pp. 1724–1731, 2006.
- [16] H. Akagi, S. Inoue, and T. Yoshii, "Control and performance of a transformerless cascade PWM STATCOM with star configuration," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 43, no. 4, pp. 1041–1049, 2007.
- [17] J. A. Barrena, L. Marroyo, M. A. Rodriguez Vidal, and J. R. Torrealday Apraiz, "Individual voltage balancing strategy for PWM cascaded H-bridge converter-based STATCOM," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 21–29, 2008.
- [18] Z. Liu, B. Liu, S. Duan, and Y. Kang, "A novel DC capacitor voltage balance control method for cascade multilevel STATCOM," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 14–27, 2012.
- [19] Q. Song and W. Liu, "Control of a cascade STATCOM with star configuration under unbalanced conditions," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 45–58, 2009.
- [20] D. Lu, J. Zhu, J. Wang, J. Yao, S. Wang, and H. Hu, "A simple zero-sequence-voltage-based cluster voltage balancing control and the negative sequence current compensation region identification for star-connected cascaded h-bridge STATCOM," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 33, no. 10, pp. 8376–8387, 2018.
- [21] Y. Neyshabouri, S. K. Chaudhary, R. Teodorescu, R. Sajadi, and H. Iman-Eini, "Improving the reactive current compensation capability of cascaded H-bridge based STATCOM under unbalanced grid voltage," *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel. Top. Power Electron.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1466–1476, 2020.
- [22] M. Hagiwara, R. Maeda, and H. Akagi, "Negative-sequence reactive-power control by a PWM STATCOM based on a modular multilevel cascade converter (MMCC-SDBC)," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 720–729, 2012.
- [23] R. Luo, Y. He, and J. Liu, "Research on the unbalanced compensation of delta-connected cascaded H-bridge multilevel SVG," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 65, no. 11, pp. 3439–3444, 2018.

- [24] J.-J. Jung, J.-H. Lee, S.-K. Sul, G. T. Son, and Y.-H. Chung, "DC capacitor voltage balancing control for delta-connected cascaded H-bridge STATCOM considering unbalanced grid and load conditions," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 4726–4735, 2018.
- [25] H. Huang, L. Zhang, O. J. Oghorada, and M. Mao, "A delta-connected MMCC-based active power conditioner for unbalanced load compensation and harmonic elimination," *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 118, p. 105811, 2020.
- [26] D. Basic, M. Geske, and S. Schroeder, "Limitations of the H-bridge multilevel STATCOMs in compensation of current imbalance," in *EPE 2015 – 17th Eur. Conf. Power Electron. Appl.*, pp. 1–10, 2015.
- [27] P. Sochor and H. Akagi, "Theoretical comparison in energy-balancing capability between star- and delta-configured modular multilevel cascade inverters for utility-scale photovoltaic systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 1980–1992, 2016.
- [28] E. Behrouzian and M. Bongiorno, "Investigation of negative-sequence injection capability of cascaded H-bridge converters in star and delta configuration," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 1675–1683, 2017.
- [29] O. J. K. Oghorada and L. Zhang, "Analysis of star and delta connected modular multilevel cascaded converter-based STATCOM for load unbalanced compensation," *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 95, pp. 341–352, 2018.
- [30] O. J. K. Oghorada and L. Zhang, "Unbalanced and reactive load compensation using an MMCC-based STATCOM with third-harmonic injection," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 66, no. 4, pp. 2891–2902, 2019.
- [31] I. Marzo, J. A. Barrena, and A. Sanchez-Ruiz, "Methodology to evaluate converter structures based on 3L NPC PEBBs," in *IECON 2020 – 46th Annu. Conf. IEEE Ind. Electron. Soc.*, pp. 4107–4114, 2020.
- [32] G. Abad, *Power Electronics and Electric Drives for Traction Applications*, G. Abad, Ed. John Wiley & Sons, 2017.
- [33] Y. Yu, G. Konstantinou, C. D. Townsend, R. P. Aguilera, and V. G. Agelidis, "Delta-connected cascaded H-bridge multilevel converters for large-scale photovoltaic grid integration," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 64, no. 11, pp. 8877–8886, 2017.
- [34] S. Ouyang, J. Liu, and H. Chen, "Arm current stress reduction technique for a delta-connected solid state transformer using zero-sequence current injection," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 36, no. 11, pp. 12234–12250, 2021.
- [35] A. G. Yepes, F. D. Freijedo, J. Doval-Gandoy, S. Lopez, J. Malvar, and P. Fernandez-Comesana, "Effects of discretization methods on the performance of resonant controllers," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 25, no. 7, pp. 1692–1712, 2010.
- [36] I. Marzo, J. A. Barrena, A. Sanchez-Ruiz, G. Abad, and I. Muguruza, "Reactive power limits of single-phase and three-phase dc-link VSC STATCOMs under negative-sequence voltage and current," in *IECON 2021 – 47th Annu. Conf. IEEE Ind. Electron. Soc.*, pp. 1–8, 2021.
- [37] A. Sanchez-Ruiz, G. Abad, I. Echeverria, I. Torre, and I. Atutxa, "Continuous phase-shifted selective harmonic elimination and DC-link voltage balance solution for H-bridge multilevel configurations, applied to 5L HNPC," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 2533–2545, 2017.